

Matrix and vectorial structures from Pascal's triangle: From Fibonacci sequence to the golden ratio

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1 Abstract

This paper studies the matrix and vector representation of the golden ratio, $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$, which is derived from the Fibonacci sequence and Pascal's triangle. The first goal of this work is to use the matrix form to analyze the terms of the Fibonacci sequence and Pascal's triangle through matrix multiplication. Moreover, the second goal is to analyze the vectorial space defined by matrix form of Pascal's triangle and represent numbers of Fibonacci and golden ratio by dot product, showing a new approach to this topic

In this article I started from examples retired by the same column of matrix form of Pascal's triangle. These examples were treated by considering its column as a sequence with its own ratio. Using this was shown a generalization to find any term of Pascal's triangle using a matrix multiplication. After that, using a matrix form, a formation pattern of numbers was written by Fibonacci's sequence and the golden ratio.

In addition, I analyzed the pattern of matrix multiplication and noticed that it represents a dot product of two vectors. With this new perspective it is possible to use tools of linear algebra to determine the vectorial space, basis and other characteristics of these vectors. Keywords: Pascal's triangle, Fibonacci's sequence, matrix, golden ratio, vectors.

2 Introduction

In mathematics, Pascal's triangle, an infinite triangular array, is an important tool that takes an essential part in probability, algebra and combinatory. It's known a variety of properties of Pascal's triangle. With this sequence it is possible to view Fibonacci numbers and construct golden ratio is a fundamental mathematical constant, known for its occurrence in nature, art, and mathematical structures.

Furthermore, this paper shows an unusual writing form using matrixes to represent and to find several terms and, with that, construct the Fibonacci's sequence. With all of this, it is possible to do the matrix form of the golden ratio. The matrix representation of these sequences permits experience a different point of view about them, allowing us to see an intriguing pattern of composition besides the traditional form.

Moreover, I expanded this matricidal representation to a vectorial analysis, then it is possible to study the vectorial space and characteristics associated with this array, expanding this sequence to vectorial structures. With that, I construct the vectorial form of Fibonacci's number and golden ratio, bringing to these structures a new perspective unusual that may have potential applications in fields such as coding theory, cryptography, and mathematical modeling, where structural patterns and vectorial relationships are fundamental.

3 Definitions

Over this paper was used the triangular Pascal's matrix.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 3 & 3 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 6 & 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 5 & 10 & 10 & 5 & 1 \\ & & & & \vdots & \end{bmatrix}$$

$$a_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i \geq 1, j = 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } j > i \\ a_{i-1,j} + a_{i-1,j-1}, & \text{if } i, j \geq 2 \end{cases} \quad \forall i, j \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

Moreover, W is a set of vectors where \vec{w}_i is the line i of pascal's matrix

$$W = \{\vec{w}_1; \vec{w}_2; \dots; \vec{w}_i\} \tag{1}$$

4 Matrix generalization of $a_{i,j}$

The purpose of this topic is to show by examples the matrix form of some $a_{i,j}$, then generalize your construction. These examples will be made by picking a term of $j = 5$ (in blue) and treating its column like a sequence with its own ratio and the construction will be done by the formation pattern of this structure $a_{i-1,j} + a_{i-1,j-1}$

4.1 Example 1

composition of $a_{7,5} = 15$:

Figure 1: Numerical sequence that forms $a_{7,5}$

The successive ratios (arrows) that make up $a_{7,5}$ corresponding to terms of $j = 4$:

$$a_{6,4} = 10 \quad ; \quad a_{5,4} = 4$$

and $j = 3$:

$$a_{5,3} = 6$$

Figure 2: Positions of the ratios

By these can be constructed the term regressing the formation pattern:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{7,5} &= a_{6,5} + a_{6,4} \\ a_{7,5} &= (a_{5,5} + a_{5,4}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) \\ a_{7,5} &= 1a_{5,5} + 2a_{5,4} + 1a_{5,3} \end{aligned}$$

Since each line is symmetric, it is possible to rewrite it by replacing $a_{5,5}$ by $a_{5,1}$ and $a_{5,4}$ by $a_{5,2}$

$$a_{7,5} = 1a_{5,1} + 2a_{5,2} + 1a_{5,3}$$

With this construction we can note that $(1; 2; 1)$ are the coefficients of the base line $(a_{5,1}; a_{5,2}; a_{5,3})$ and can be done the matrix form of the term:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} [a_{5,1} \quad a_{5,2} \quad a_{5,3}] = a_{7,5}$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{3,1} \\ a_{3,2} \\ a_{3,3} \end{bmatrix} [a_{5,1} \quad a_{5,2} \quad a_{5,3}] = a_{7,5}$$

4.2 Example 2

composition of $a_{8,5} = 35$:

Figure 3: Numerical sequence that forms $a_{8,5}$

The successive ratios (arrows) that make up $a_{8,5}$ corresponding to terms of $j = 4$:

$$a_{7,4} = 20; \quad a_{6,4} = 10 \quad ; \quad a_{5,4} = 4$$

$j = 3$:

$$a_{6,3} = 10 \quad ; \quad a_{5,3} = 6$$

And $j = 2$:

$$a_{5,2} = 4$$

Figure 4: Positions of the ratios

By these can be constructed the term regressing the formation pattern:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{8,5} &= a_{7,5} + a_{6,4} \\
a_{8,5} &= (a_{5,5} + a_{5,4}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{6,4} + a_{6,3}) \\
a_{8,5} &= [(a_{5,5} + a_{5,4}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3})] + [(a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,2} + a_{5,3})] \\
a_{8,5} &= 1a_{5,5} + 3a_{5,4} + 3a_{5,3} + 1a_{5,2}
\end{aligned}$$

Since each line is symmetric, it is possible to rewrite it by replacing $a_{5,5}$ by $a_{5,1}$ and $a_{5,4}$ by $a_{5,2}$

$$a_{8,5} = 1a_{5,1} + 3a_{5,2} + 3a_{5,3} + 1a_{5,4}$$

With this construction we can note that $(1; 3; 3; 1)$ are the coefficients of the base line $(a_{5,1}; a_{5,2}; a_{5,3}; a_{5,4})$ and can be done the matrix form of the term:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \\ 3 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} [a_{5,1} \quad a_{5,2} \quad a_{5,3} \quad a_{5,4}] = a_{8,5}$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{4,1} \\ a_{4,2} \\ a_{4,3} \\ a_{4,4} \end{bmatrix} [a_{5,1} \quad a_{5,2} \quad a_{5,3} \quad a_{5,4}] = a_{8,5}$$

4.3 Example 2

composition of $a_{9,5} = 70$:

Figure 5: Numerical sequence that forms $a_{9,5}$

The successive ratios (arrows) that make up $a_{8,5}$ corresponding to terms of $j = 4$:

$$a_{8,4} = 35; \quad a_{7,4} = 20; \quad a_{6,4} = 10 \quad ; \quad a_{5,4} = 4$$

$j = 3:$

$$a_{7,3} = 15; \quad a_{6,3} = 10; \quad a_{5,3} = 6$$

$j = 2:$

$$a_{6,2} = 5 \quad a_{5,2} = 4$$

And $j = 1:$

$$a_{5,1} = 1$$

Figure 6: Positions of the ratios

By these can be constructed the term regressing the formation pattern:

$$a_{9,5} = a_{8,5} + a_{8,4}$$

$$a_{9,5} = [(a_{5,5} + a_{5,4}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,2} + a_{5,3})] + (a_{7,4} + a_{7,3})$$

$$a_{9,5} = [(a_{5,5} + a_{5,4}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,4} + a_{5,3})] + [(a_{5,4} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,2} + a_{5,3}) + (a_{5,2} + a_{5,1}) + (a_{5,2} + a_{5,3})]$$

$$a_{9,5} = 1a_{5,1} + 4a_{5,2} + 6a_{5,3} + 4a_{5,4} + 1a_{5,5}$$

With this construction we can note that $(1; 4; 6; 4; 1)$ are the coefficients of the base line $(a_{5,1}; a_{5,2}; a_{5,3}; a_{5,4}; a_{5,5})$ and can be done the matrix form of the term:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 4 \\ 6 \\ 4 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_{5,1} & a_{5,2} & a_{5,3} & a_{5,4} & a_{5,5} \end{bmatrix} = a_{9,5}$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{5,1} \\ a_{5,2} \\ a_{5,3} \\ a_{5,4} \\ a_{5,5} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_{5,1} & a_{5,2} & a_{5,3} & a_{5,4} & a_{5,5} \end{bmatrix} = a_{9,5}$$

4.4 Theorem

By these examples, we can note that the construction of an $a_{i,j}$ is done by the multiplication of two matrices (or two vectors). The first matrix M_p^T is a transposed line of the matrix that referred to the position of the term at the column. this position is done by counting beginning the first positive term of the column and can be expressed as $p = i - j + 1$

To elucidate this we can construct the example 3 that is $a_{9,5}$:

$$\begin{aligned} p &= i - j + 1 \\ p_{a_{9,5}} &= 9 - 5 + 1 = 5 \end{aligned}$$

It means that the first matrix of $a_{9,5}$ is the line 5 of the matrix (1; 4; 6; 4; 1)

$$M_p^T = \vec{w}_{i-j+1} \quad (2)$$

In addition, by the examples, the another matrix M_f is another line of the matrix. This is a fixed matrix, it means that all term of a column j uses the same M_f^T

$$M_f = \vec{w}_j \quad (3)$$

Then, we can write an $a_{i,j}$:

$$a_{i,j} = M_p^T M_f \quad (4)$$

$$a_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{i-j+1,1} \\ a_{i-j+1,2} \\ a_{i-j+1,3} \\ \vdots \\ a_{i-j+1,i-j+1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_{j,1} & a_{j,2} & a_{j,3} & \dots & a_{j,j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$a_{i,j} = \langle w_{i-j+1}, w_j \rangle \quad (6)$$

4.4.1 Proof

We can make an induction in lines. Suppose that the theorem is true for any $i \leq n$, it means that exists a relation between an term of the matrix and the inner product of two lines. It is clearly true for $i, j = 1$. That is because:

$$a_{1,1} = \langle w_1, w_1 \rangle$$

Note that $a_{1,1}$ depends on its own line, but the line 1 is previously defined. Now the following part has to be proven:

$$a_{n+1,j} = \langle w_{(n+1)-j+1}, w_j \rangle$$

We know that

$$a_{n+1,j} = a_{n,j} + a_{n,j-1}$$

Assuming that the theorem is true, the next implication is also true

$$a_{n+1,j} = \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1} \rangle$$

By the properties of the Pascal triangle, we can create a dislocate line

$$w_k^d = [0 \quad w_k]$$

and

$$w_j = w_{j-1}^d + w_{j-1}$$

Now, the inner product can be written in another way

$$\begin{aligned} a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+2}, [w_j - w_{j-1}^d] \rangle \\ a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle - \langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1}^d \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\langle w_{n-j+2}, w_j \rangle$ is our main object. With that, we can conclude that the rest of equation must be equal to zero

$$\begin{aligned} \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle - \langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1}^d \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle &= \langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1}^d \rangle \\ \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle &= a_{n,j} \end{aligned}$$

So that theorem is true, the next relation must be true

$$\langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1}^d \rangle = a_{n,j}$$

It construct a new relation between a inner product involving a dislocate line and an $a_{i,j}$ that will be proven next by another induction. Following the pattern involving the passage o $d = 0$ to $d = 1$, we have

$$a_{n,j} = \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle = \langle w_{n-j+2}, w_{j-1}^d \rangle = \dots = \langle w_{n-j+1+m}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle$$

Utilizing the same pattern with the dislocate lines we have

$$\begin{aligned} a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle \\ a_{n+1,j} &= a_{n,j} + a_{n,j-1} \\ a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+m+1}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m-1}^{d_m} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

we know that

$$w_{j-m}^{d_m} = w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}} + w_{j-m-1}^{d_m}$$

we can interpret the inner product with this new relation

$$\begin{aligned} a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+m+1}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, [w_{j-m}^{d_m} - w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}}] \rangle \\ a_{n+1,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+m+1}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle + \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle - \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle$ is our main object and we need that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle - \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}} \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle &= \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}} \rangle \\ a_{n,j} &= \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m}^{d_m} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

So, is true that

$$a_{n,j} = \langle w_{n-j+m+2}, w_{j-m-1}^{d_{m+1}} \rangle$$

d_{m+1} is the next expansion for the pattern that I suppose to be true for d_m . This expansion does not proof the theorem, but guarantees that if the theorem is true, it goes for any dislocate line.

The proof will be done by regressing an $a_{i,j}$ using the property of the triangle, the same form of the examples from the previous section.

$$a_{n,j} = a_{n-1,j} + a_{n-1,j-1}$$

$$a_{n,j} = (a_{n-2,j} + a_{n-2,j-1}) + (a_{n-2,j-1} + a_{n-2,j-2})$$

$$a_{n,j} = a_{n-2,j} + 2 \cdot a_{n-2,j-1} + a_{n-2,j-2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{n,j} &= [(a_{n-3,j} + a_{n-3,j-1}) + (a_{n-3,j-1} + a_{n-3,j-2})] + \\ & \quad [(a_{n-3,j-1} + a_{n-3,j-2}) + (a_{n-3,j-2} + a_{n-3,j-3})] \end{aligned}$$

$$a_{n,j} = a_{n-3,j} + 3 \cdot a_{n-3,j-1} + 3 \cdot a_{n-3,j-2} + a_{n-3,j-3}$$

Note that after iteration we have a new configuration for $a_{i,j}$, for each step the coefficients are changed, starting from terms of line two, but these three constructions are limited by some values of n and j , then we need to expand for an arbitrary term. With these steps, after k iterations we have terms of line $k+1$.

$$a_{n,j} = a_{n-k,j} + k \cdot a_{n-k,j-2} + \dots + k \cdot a_{n-k,j-k+1} + a_{n-k,j-k}$$

The limit case occurs when $k = j-1$, that is because we will have the last term as $a_{n-j-2,1}$, building a hole line.

$$a_{n,j} = a_{n-j+1,j} + (j-1) \cdot a_{n-j+1,j-1} + \dots + (j-1) \cdot a_{n-j+1,j-k+1} + a_{n-j+1,1}$$

We can see that the coefficients corresponds to terms of line j , and the another terms corresponds to line $i - j + 1$. Then we can rewrite by another form

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{n-j+1,j} \\ a_{n-j+1,j-1} \\ a_{n-j+1,j-2} \\ \vdots \\ a_{n-j+1,1} \end{bmatrix} [a_{j,1} \quad a_{j,2} \quad a_{j,3} \quad \dots \quad a_{j,j}] = a_{n,j}$$

And this is the inner product of two lines

$$a_{n,j} = \langle w_{n-j+1}, w_j \rangle$$